

Application of Scientific Evidence as to the Main Argument in Determining the Causality of Doctors' Actions

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 26, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Scientific Evidence, Legal Certainty, Ius Curia Novit</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6296612</p>	<p><i>The emergence of facts of death in the case of a doctor's negligence must obtain legal reasoning based on critical thinking. By thinking critically, the medico-legal opinion given is guaranteed more logical, both clinical cases in the medical field and juridical cases in the field of law, it is necessary to develop arguments that are full of causal related requires the explanation of forensic medicine experts as the main argument(central argument). This concerns the technical issue of reliable empirical clarification of facts.Medicolegal case resolution requires the formation of a solid argument by not mixing the two disciplines into the analysis of the case.Determining the size and requirements of whether the doctor's actions have committed a professional error or not, to what extent the doctor's actions can be legally protected, it is necessary to trace the causality chain to find a direct cause argumentatively based on scientific evidence in the enforcement of the causality of doctors' actions.</i></p>

Introduction

Judging from criminal law, the importance of proving the facts of death through valid evidence before the trial, including analysis and valid reasoning, needs to be investigated how to determine the main cause as a condition for the occurrence of a crime based on a causal *verband* (Sofian, 2018).The causal *verband* in question is very casuistic if you use a simple causality theory. Considering the complexity of the consequences (*post-factum*) requires the main argument (*central argument*) related to scientific legal decision making with different levels of the spectrum, from simple to complex, or intuitive to probabilistic categories (Herkutanto, 2021).In the analysis of medical cases, mathematical calculations are used to determine the probability of a certain way of death. Sometimes the cause of death of a person can be obtained, but the mechanism of death remains uncertain. Likewise, the cause of a person's death can be obtained, but sometimes the events behind the mechanism of death cannot be revealed (Sampurna, 2012).Medicolegal analysis approach of existing health status, by exploring other causal factors, or the doctor's own actions. The pattern takes into account possible variables among the possible injury factors, which is carried out with regular and systematic examinations.

It is not easy to establish a doctor's diagnosis and therapy, which is influenced by medical science itself, causing technical problems with a more difficult complexity when determining the main cause of the many other causes for the clarification of facts based on a critical way of thinking (Dubé,&Gallina, 2006).This is where the chain of events is arranged in a sequencethat contains causality accurately and more guaranteed precision (Cottrell, 2008)and morecan be maintained (Willingham, 2007).

The function of forming *medico-legal* arguments is important, which emphasizes the fact that the entire contents of the formulation of a criminal offense that the public prosecutor has indicted in his indictment are based on solid arguments (Tomassi, 1995).Regarding the determination of the size and requirements by placing the responsibility of the doctor on whether he has committed a professional error, first of all, to prove the connection between the doctor's actions and to what extent can be legally protected.This makes it easier for the public prosecutor to develop information on the examination of evidence.

When associated with evidence-based arguments according to the level of complexity of medical cases, then the evidence is reliable and creates legal liability. In order to seek the truth of a fact (Evans, 2010), while at the same time shed light on a legal event against the conception of the judge's findings and how judges know how to draw conclusions and methods for formulating expert opinions on medicolegal causality using an evidence-based framework (evidence-based practice).

Although the legal system already has a law of proof that regulates the acceptance (admissible) of expert testimony (Prodjohamidjoyo, 2003).However, the acceptable evidence, judges must be scientifically based with an expert background have reporting standards or guidelines in forensic medicine. This concept seen as more consistent is a terminology related to science based on the complexity of the case. In handling complex cases, the courts often must rely on expert testimony which is nothing more than a clinical judgment based on

debatable experience, while the method used by experts is required to be "transparent" and can be accounted for based on arguments in a reliable and accountable manner (Got, 1986).

Scientific Evidence, Legal Certainty, and Ius Curia Novit

The process of proving the causality of the doctor's actions uses three components, namely scientific evidence, legal certainty, and *Ius curia Novit*. According to scientific evidence on YahyaHarahap(2009),AtangRanoemiharja(2008), and Soeparmono (2002), who are three criminal experts that have the same views related to scientific evidence. The three criminal experts explained that scientific evidence is classified as forensic medicine, or judicial medical science is needed for the benefit of criminal justice (*strafrechtspleging*) which is related to several legal provisions of criminal law, formal or substantial, by using knowledge medicine scientifically. The concept of proof based on an oath of office is what is examined and found on living, corpse or physical evidence, or other evidence (Soeparmono, 2002).¹³ Ian Dennis interprets as, "real evidence is a term used to refer to physical objects produced for the court inspection" (Hiariej, 2002). Thus, scientific evidence explains the evidence that refers to the physical object of examination at trial using principles and techniques basic sciences of biology, chemistry, and physics to retrieve information to solve the problems related to criminal law (Sullivan & Rosen, 2010).

With the proposed *gerechtelijketoxicology*, dactyloscopy, *sporenkunde*, ballistics which are essentially physics, chemistry, mathematics (sometimes applied) and can be used (*aangewend*) for the benefit of criminal justice. In connection with the provisions regarding autopsies and post-mortem (*lijkschouwingen*) in medical science, the judiciary can assist the implementation of criminal justice as a reflection in the Criminal Procedure Code which is stated in Article 133 (Adji, 1991). not only applied medical science, but also *VeR* issues as valid and recognized evidence.

Then, in the principle of legal certainty, as Utrecht stated, it explained the presence of law to ensure legal certainty (*rechtzekerheid*) in human association. Not certainty of action against, or action in accordance with the rule of law (Arrasjid, 2008). A regulation made and promulgated must definitely be regulated clearly and logically without causing multiple interpretations. In other words, legal certainty can be obtained if in a situation there are clear, consistent, and easy to obtain legal rules.

Meanwhile, the concept is based on the adage *Ius Curia Novit/Curia Novit Jus*, where judges are considered to know and understand everything the law is a case, the court understands the law (Derlén, 2009). Judges are deemed to understand all laws, so that the court may not refuse to examine and adjudicate and decide cases submitted on the pretext that the law is absent or unclear. This is explained in Article 10 paragraph (1) of the *UU Judicial Power*, the court adjudicates according to the law without "discriminating against people".

A judge must have deep and broad knowledge and insight about the law, so even the most recent laws, because judges must not stop learning and must constantly update their knowledge and understanding of the law and its dynamics (Wibowo, 2009). The judge has the authority to determine which objective law must be applied (*toepassing*) in accordance with the subject matter of the case concerning the legal relationship of the litigating parties in the concrete (Harahap, 2005). By finding and applying the law objectively, it is absolutely the duty and authority of the judge, not the rights and authorities of the parties. The parties are not obliged to prove what law is applied, because the judge is deemed to understand.

Judges as justice goalkeepers are required to apply the principle *Ius Curia Novit* in every decision. The judge's decision as a form of the judge's statement in his position as a state official must contain the settlement of cases which is a whole series of processes examination of a case (Alkotsar, 2009). The existence of this *Ius Curia Novit* principle as the judge's guidelines produce decisions with legal certainty. In a case related to medicine, the judge must pass his verdict using a scientific approach according to the complexity of the case. unless then legal certainty will not be achieved.

Doctor's Action Causality Analysis

Based on an inductive analysis where the line of thinking starts from the current health status in the form of personal injury or damage. At a certain event or other event, people easily say the personal injury is caused by the event. In fact, the injuries seen can be caused not only by the alleged event, but also by health status (existing health conditions/original disease) or intervening factors (intervention factors/patient behavior) from the condition of pre-existing disease in the past (past), or health conditions in the future (future), and various intervening conditions for future health conditions (Hannon & Knapp, 2008).

Scientifically, to place the accident and effect relationship method through a series of mechanisms, temporality, and outcome determinants. On mechanisms, there is the logic of physics, kinetics, biomechanics, physiology, pathogenesis which explains the effect after an accident. On temporality, emphasized the importance of "sequence of events and continuity", or events that cause an effect after one accident. On outcome determinants, the existence of external determinants that may play a role, for example, environment, socio-culture, medication adherence, etc. Tracing this link aims to find a direct cause through a series of scientific

methods by forensic and medicolegal experts argumentative. This is where scientific evidence is often overlooked in the enforcement of the causality of doctors' actions (Hannon & Knapp, 2008).

Deductively, interpreting what has been regulated by law is applied to the actual situation in the event (Dubé & Gallina, 2006). This process is parallel with the indictment of Article 359 of the Criminal Code, how is medical logic in the logic of science? The law aligns with the historical aspects of the law negatively. Substantially, the process can empirically strengthen the causes of death of the victim, whether it includes serious, moderate, or minor injuries to determine the type of treatment given to the victim with the highest accuracy (Herikutanto, 2005). This enforcement of causality emphasizes the relationship of the *culpa lata* to the effect according to the implementation mechanism agreed upon by the medical community (Adji, 1991).

About the principle of *Ius Curia Novit*, although it is still considered a theory and assumptions, in reality, the assumption is considered wrong, because no matter how vast a judge's experience is, it's impossible to know the whole law which is so broad and complex. This adage was put forward for strengthening the functions and obligations of judges to hear cases examined under the law, not outside the law (Suwasta, 2011). In its application, enhancing the judge's belief must be generated from two tools: evidence that has been supported by clear and rational reasons for making a decision (Mulyadi, 2007). The concept of establishing causality will link scientific evidence and legal certainty attached to *Ius Curia Novit* in the judge's consideration.

The purpose of the analysis of the three components is to explain scientific evidence as the base for legal certainty becomes an indicator in capturing empirical facts are based on critical thinking which only can be enforced should the rules in critical thinking be met. The principle of medicolegal causality in the form of (medical opinion) requires all elements of critical thinking are "relevance" as a condition for a cause-effect, with the precise accuracy of the argument medicolegal that is more secure (Cottrell, 1990) clearer and more defensible (Willingham, 2007).⁶ and free from bias due to emotions and thinking errors (fallacies) (Fearnside & Holther, 1959) In these three components explain the estimated causes of death as a breaker in the chain of causality.

In the context of legal science as a whole, the reasoning mechanism both inductive and deductive reasoning is needed to explain facts which is more structured to conclude. Understanding and knowledge of logic are needed for legal practitioners who deal with legal issues. Here legal reasoning is not a different kind of reasoning and is separated from the logic of philosophy as the science of how to think properly, but how to apply the rules of thinking according to logic in the field of law (Weruin, 2017).

In the medical law aspect, the occurrence of a claim that asks for the doctor's responsibility is not only based on expert opinion but is necessary to put a scientific argument whether the actions of doctors are really the main cause (direct causation). In its application, placing away thinking in harmony between doctors, lawyers, and forensic experts (Herikutanto & Abdoellah, 2021).

According to von Kries in Utrecht, the cause of an action that results from that act is previously known/estimated by the perpetrator. Thus, these facts can sharpen the *adequate* theory that will be put forward by the judge with the fulfillment of all the contents of the formulation of a crime as one piece of empirical evidence which is then assembled in scientific knowledge and conclude whether the doctor's actions are the culprit. In placing an event according to the context of space and time hence the wider meaning of the *Ver* evidence that puts a person's rights at stake (Sofian, 2018).

Conclusion

The scientific evidence approach makes legal certainty against a doctor's crime, especially on the unsatisfactory theoretical nature explanations. Scientific evidence has a spectrum from simple to complex. Simple cases can be analyzed using an intuitive approach, but the more complex the case must be analyzed using an increasingly probabilistic approach. To what extent the concept of scientific-based causal verbs is in line with scientific thinking through observation, hypotheses, gathering evidence, testing facts found to reach a conclusion. The purpose of utilizing scientific evidence is to obtain a legal responsibility decision that is materially understood to achieve the real truth as the basis for judges' considerations.

Main Point

1. In medical cases, the judge must pass the verdict using a scientific approach according to the complexity of the case.
2. In its application, establishing a harmonious way of thinking between doctors, experts in law, and forensic experts with scientific thinking through observation, hypotheses, gathering evidence, testing the facts to reach a conclusion.
3. Scientific evidence has a spectrum from simple to complex. A simple case can be analyzed using an intuitive approach, but in the case of getting more complex the case must be analyzed using an increasingly probabilistic.

4. The proof process is carried out more towards material truth rather than determining the doctor's error, tends to be procedural rather than punishment of doctors as the application of multi-disciplinary science.
5. As a central argument that contains the results of causality, it is considered different from a clinical medical diagnosis due to the lack of inherent causal analysis.

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